

Grant Agreement No: 101004761

AIDAInnova

Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures project AIDAINNOVA

MILESTONE REPORT

STATUS REPORT ON DIGITIZATION

MILESTONE: MS39

Document identifier:	AIDAInnova-MS39
Due date of milestone:	End of Month 33 (January 2024)
Report release date:	01/03/2024
Work package:	WP9: Cryogenic Detectors
Lead beneficiary:	CNRS/IP2I
Document status:	Final

Abstract:

Task 9.3 foresees the study of a novel charge readout scheme for very large time projection chambers named Vertical Drift. This technology avoids using wire chambers to collect the signals of the electrons from charged particles ionization, at the end of their drift path. This kind of development program, included in task 9.3, is unprecedented and totally innovative in the domain of LAr Time Projection Chambers (TPC). In Vertical Drift wire chambers instead are replaced by stacks of perforated printed circuit boards integrated in Charge Readout Planes (CRP) of $3 \times 3.3 \text{ m}^2$ placed to cover the surface at the top of the detector. This active surface receives the electrons drifting thanks to a uniform electric field aligned along the vertical axis. The cryogenic ASIC amplifiers used to read the signals are integrated in this layout in front-end cards hosted in cryostat penetrations ‘signal feedthrough chimneys’ which make them accessible from the outside during detector operation. The digitization electronics at warm is cabled to warm flanges closing the top part of the chimneys. This technology, which is foreseen to equip the second DUNE Far Detector module, underwent in 2021-2022 extensive large-scale tests at the CERN Neutrino Platform. These tests successfully demonstrated its validity. This milestone reports on the work and developments performed on the CRPs readout system.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2024

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

The Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators (AIDAinnova) project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101004761. AIDAinnova began in April 2021 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

Task 9.3 deals with the developments associated to the demonstration of the Vertical Drift (VD) charge readout technology which is a novel design of LAr TPC detectors based on the use of perforated printed circuit boards instead of wire planes for the readout of the ionization signals in LAr Time Projection Chambers (TPC).

The Vertical Drift design is particularly suited to build and instrument very large LAr detectors in a simpler and cost effective way. VD is foreseen to be deployed for the second DUNE Far Detector module (FD-2). Task 9.3 focuses on the demonstration of the configuration for the readout of the top-drift volume of FD2 by developing an optimized configuration for the Charge Readout Planes (CRP) and their associated electronics. The Charge Readout Planes host the perforated Printed Circuit Boards anode planes and are used in order to collect the ionization signals from the TPC drift volume and provide a 3 independent views imaging of the tracks left by charged particles in liquid argon. This charge is then amplified by cryogenic ASIC amplifiers hosted in the chimneys and then digitized by microTCA electronics on the cryostat roof.

This milestone status report includes the results from an intensive prototyping campaign on the Vertical Drift technology, which was conducted in 2021-2022 using the infrastructure provided by the CERN Neutrino Platform, including a dedicated Cold-Box cryostat of the exact size of a VD Charge Readout Plane unit. This campaign included the successful development and tests of the first two Charge Readout Planes corresponding to the final layout foreseen for the top drift volume of FD2 and of their associated electronics and signal feedthrough chimneys.

1. INTRODUCTION

Task 9.3 Vertical Drift (VD) Charge Readout is a detector development oriented to the construction of the second DUNE LAr Far Detector module (FD-2). Vertical Drift is a completely innovative technique that allows reading the ionization of charged tracks in LAr Time Projection Chambers without instrumenting the anode surface with wire planes but by exploiting Charge Readout Plane (CRP) units (each one covering $3 \times 3.3 \text{ m}^2$ active surface) made of two layers of perforated anode Printed Circuit Boards (PCB). The anode perforated PCBs copper layers are segmented in strips of about 5 mm pitch in order to define readout views. The two PCB layers provide two views (at ± 30 degrees (with respect to the beam direction in FD-2) reading induction signal and a last view at 90 degrees collecting the electrons. The Vertical Drift layout and the use of perforated anodes instead of wire planes make the construction and installation of very large size detectors cheaper and effective.

The anode planes are coupled to dedicated cryogenic Front-End (FE) and digitization warm electronics (altogether defined as: Top Drift Electronics, TDE) explicitly developed and optimized for this configuration present in the upper part of the drift volume of the DUNE VD Far Detector module. Special mechanical cryostat penetrations “Chimneys” host the FE boards with cryogenic amplifiers, preserving their accessibility at any time without interfering with the detector operation. Vertical Drift is an evolution and further simplification of the Dual-Phase technique already developed in AIDA-2020. Both the Dual-Phase and Vertical Drift developments have been strongly supported by the CERN Neutrino Platform infrastructure located in the EHN1 hall.

The demonstration at large scale of this unprecedented detector technology, corresponding to the Vertical Drift for the DUNE top drift volume of FD-2, is the goal of task 9.3 and it represents an essential step before moving to the construction of the DUNE FD-2. In the years 2021 and 2022, CRP planes with perforated anodes were constructed and tested, together with the associated readout electronics and chimneys, at the CERN Neutrino Platform with a dedicated cold-box cryostat, capable of hosting and running in LAr TPC configuration a complete VD CRP.

The tests campaign at the CERN Neutrino Platform foresaw the test of the first Vertical Drift CRP (CRP1, shared CRP including both top-drift and bottom-drift) configurations in the fall of 2021, including two consecutive cold-box runs. CRP1 was tested again in a version CRP1b including some improvements of the grounding for the bottom-drift readout in May-June 2022 with a new cold-box test. The year 2022 was crucial in order to test in the cold-box the first two complete versions (CRP2 and CRP3) of Vertical Drift CRPs with their final strips layout configuration foreseen for DUNE FD-2. These tests were successfully accomplished between July and November 2022, providing excellent results that validated the CRP design. All these cold-box tests were based on the same readout configuration of the Top Drift Electronics including the front-end analog cards hosting the ASIC amplifiers and the microTCA digitization electronics. These elements represent all innovative developments of the Top Drift Electronics. This milestone reports on the readout electronics developments occurred since 2021 and on its integration, with the goal of demonstrating the Vertical Drift technology, pursued by task 9.3.

2. ACTIVITIES AND RESULTS

2.1. VERTICAL DRIFT COLD-BOX TESTS AND TOP DRIFT ELECTRONICS DEVELOPMENTS

Vertical Drift Charge Readout Planes (CRPs) with perforated anodes were constructed and tested at the CERN Neutrino Platform with a dedicated Cold-Box (CB) cryostat. The year 2021 saw a very intensive test program at the CERN Neutrino Platform in the EHN1 hall, where a new Cold-Box (CB) cryostat was equipped nearby the NP02 cryostat, in order to share the same cryogenics system, for the tests of the Vertical Drift CRPs [1]. The Cold-Box has exactly the footprint capable of containing a single CRP module. The CB can be operated in Time Projection Chamber configuration with 30 cm vertical drift space located in between the CRP lower surface and the cathode plane. This drift distance allows collecting very large samples (order of millions) of cosmic rays that can be exploited to fully characterize the CRP behavior and of its associated electronics, both covered by task 9.3. The CRP is suspended from the roof of the Cold-Box (Figure 1) that can be inserted and extracted from the top of the Cold-Box in order to seal the cold-box cryostat and define the detector configuration with the drift space in the TPC (Figure 2).

Fig. 1: A Vertical Drift top-drift Charge Readout Plane (CRP2) suspended from the cold-box roof while being transported to the cold-box location. The copper bottom surface of the first layer of perforated anodes PCBs is visible from below. On the sides one can see the flat cables bringing signals from the anodes to the chimneys hosting the cryogenic readout amplifiers

In order to test the CRPs at warm, while allowing the access to them during the tests, and optimize their electrical configuration and check all connectors a complementary setup to the Cold-box (the Faraday Cage) was also developed and built in 2022.

Fig. 2: Cold-box cryostat built for the tests in TPC mode of the Vertical Drift Charge Readout Planes. This top view shows at the top the cold-box roof with the CRP suspended below while being lowered in order to close the cold-box cryostat (at the bottom) with a cathode module laying on its floor

The Faraday cage (Figure 3) is closed at its top by the cold-box roof with the CRP suspended below. This configuration allows performing for each CRP first a test at warm in the Faraday Cage and then move the roof to the cold-Box in order to perform the test at cold with liquid argon in TPC mode. The Faraday cage completely shields the CRP strips from picking up, as antennas, EMI noise from the environment, while preserving complete access for people and working space around the CRP during tests. In 2022 all CRP tests (CRP1b, CRP2, CRP3) were systematically conducted in two steps: a first operation at warm in the Faraday cage in order to cross-checks the noise levels and the electrical connection and then an extensive run in the cold-box filled with LAr and operated in TPC mode.

Fig. 3: CRP2 while being tested at warm in the Faraday cage setup before undergoing a cold-box test. The CRP is suspended from the cold-box roof which closes the top side of the Faraday Cage. The cold-box roof is fully instrumented with the analogue readout electronics and the uTCA digitization system and in a cold-box test in TPC mode.

The analog cryogenic amplifiers are hosted at the bottom of the chimneys (Figure 4). The chimneys are pipes going through the insulation of the roof of the cryostat until reaching a location, inside the cryostat gas ullage, very close to the CRP. The bottom of each chimney is sealed by a cold flange printed circuit board (Fig. 4) that prevents from contaminating the ultra-pure LAr environment of the cryostat during access to the FE electronics or chimney operation. The FE cards with the cryogenic amplifiers (Figure 5), mounted on blades, are plugged on connectors located on the top surface of the cold flange PCB. The bottom side of the cold flange has connectors that are used to plug flat cables bringing the signals (from charge collection or induction views) from the CRP. The FE cards operate at a temperature of about 110 K present in the cryostat ullage space. The chimney is closed at the top with a vertical warm flange that includes the connector to cable the amplified signals to the digitization electronics contained in uTCA crates on the cryostat roof and it is filled with N₂ in order to avoid humidity condensation on the FE cards. Five chimneys are integrated on the cold-box roof in order to allow for the tests of the top-drift charge readout planes.

Both the FE cards and the microTCA digitization boards (AMC) have the same channels granularity of 64 channels per board and are connected 1:1 in the readout chain. Each microTCA crate is hosting up to 10 AMC boards. The AMC boards (Figure 6) exploit commercial ADC chips (AD9257) in order to sample the analog signals at 2.5 MHz. On each AMC board the readout of the ADC is operated by an FPGA (Cyclone V) running a virtual NIOS II processor. The FPGA collects the data from the ADCs and formats them in UDP packets (jumbo frames) transmitted to the DAQ backend on the ethernet network. Each AMC board has a 10 Gbit/s connectivity to the uTCA crate backplane. The synchronization of the sampling of the AMC boards and the knowledge of the UTC time for each ADC sample with ~ns accuracy is ensured by a dedicated White-Rabbit board (WR-MCH) inserted in each microTCA crate, exploiting the backplane to deliver the timing and clock signals to each AMC. This timing distribution system is also an innovative development of the top-drift electronics of task 9.3.

Each microTCA crate has a MicroTCA Carrier Hub (MCH) containing an ethernet switch connected via the backplane to the single AMC boards. The MCH is capable of handling a total bandwidth of 120 Gbit/s with an external connectivity organized in three uplink ports of 40 Gbit/s each. For the DUNE application, an MCH connectivity via a single 40 Gbit/s port is exploited and connected to the DAQ back-end. The 40Gbit/s uplink of the MCH has about 50% bandwidth occupancy. The system used for the cold-box tests represented the very first large-scale application of a microTCA system with 40 Gbit/s connectivity involving a readout system with 200 Gbit/s total bandwidth.

Fig. 4: (Left) Illustration of a signal feedthrough chimney hosting the cryogenic amplifiers and going through the cryostat insulation (closed view and section of the chimney pipe showing the blade with the FE card plugged on the cold flange) (Right) view of the top of the system with the microTCA crates for the current implementation in the Cold-Box tests for the Vertical Drift.

Fig. 5: Picture of a Top-Drift Electronics analogue front-end board hosting four 16 channels cryogenic ASIC amplifiers (64 readout channels per board)

Fig. 6: Picture of a microTCA Top-Drift Electronics AMC digitization board

The first CRP prototype (CRP1) was successfully tested in November-December 2021. This CRP was shared among the top-drift, on which task 9.3 is focused, (TDE) and bottom-drift (BDE) readouts developed for the DUNE Vertical Drift Far Detector module. This CRP was re-tested both in the Faraday cage and in the cold-box in May-June 2022 (CRP1b) after having implemented some grounding improvements needed by the BDE readout. This test was the occasion also to check the stability of the response after a long time and several manipulations occurred to the CRP.

Following the tests on CRP1, and physics optimization studies based on simulations of the reconstruction of neutrino events in FD-2, the Vertical Drift channels layout and strip orientation (3 views at 90°, +30° and -30° with respect to the beam) (Fig.7) were finalized in a common geometry for the top-drift and bottom-drift CRPs. This configuration was primarily implemented and tested in 2022 on CRP2 and CRP3, which represent the first Vertical Drift CRPs with the final layout and are both top-drift CRPs. The channels counting corresponds to 48 FE cards (hosted in 5 chimneys) and 48 AMC digitization cards (hosted in 5 uTCA crates) per CRP, for a total of 3072 charge readout channels. The first full-size top-drift CRP (CRP2) was constructed and tested in July 2022 during the continuation of the cold box tests campaign foreseen in 2022 (Fig.8). A second first full-size top-drift CRP (CRP3), with the same strips layout of CRP2, was also fully tested in October 2022.

Fig. 7: Final layout of the strips segmentation implemented on the stack of anode perforated PCBs constituting CRP2

Fig. 8: Cold-Box roof top view during CRP2 operation with 5 chimneys each one cabled to a uTCA digitization crate (black boxes)

In the CRP stack two perforated anode PCBs (each one 3.2 mm thick) segmented in strip with a pitch going from 5.1 to 7.65 mm ensure 3 independent views. The first perforated PCB facing the drift volume has only its top face readout with copper strips implementing an induction view (Induction 1). A bipolar signal is induced by the approach and departure of the electrons along their trajectories on Induction 1 by the flow of electrons coming from the drift volume and passing through the holes of the perforated PCB (2.4 mm diameter). The electrons then continue their path (see Fig. 7) passing through the holes of the second perforated PCB. There they leave an induction signal on the bottom

layers segmented in the induction 2 strips and eventually they are collected by the strips implemented on the top layer of this second PCB (Collection View). The PCB surfaces are set at progressively higher voltages (see Fig.) which are needed to define the electrons flow through the holes in such a way that the induction views are transparent, and the electrons are collected only by the last view. The signals from the different readout layers implemented on the stack of the two perforated PCBs are collected at the sides of the CRP by “edge cards” routing the signals to adapter boards at the top of the CRP hosting the connectors to plug the flat cables which will then bring these signals to the chimneys. This readout solution guarantees the routing of the signals introducing little dead space on the CRP sides.

In 2022 the Cold-Box tests of the final CRP layout demonstrated the good performance of the CRP and of its associated electronics, including the operation of the chimneys. The results were completely fulfilling expectations. A very large statistics of cosmic ray tracks was collected to characterize the stable operation of the detector and the uniformity response of the CRP. A typical event containing cosmic ray tracks is shown in Fig. 9. This test program fully demonstrated the Vertical Drift readout. The two final top-drift CRPs (CRP2 and CRP3) have then been integrated at the end of 2023 inside the NP02 cryostat for the global Module-0 integration test (ProtoDUNE-VD).

Fig. 9: Example of clean cosmic ray tracks collected during the operation of CRP2 in the Cold-Box

Cold box operation runs repeated at large time distance on the same CRP, after several thermal cycles and manipulation on the CRP structures, demonstrated the robustness of the CRPs and of its readout system and the reproducibility of the detector operation and results. This is shown in Figure 10, where the dE/dx response measured on CRP1/CRP1b with large samples of cosmic ray tracks is compared between the November 2021 and June 2022 runs. The two Landau distributions in black and red measured at different epochs are perfectly overlaying.

Calorimetry through time

- dQ/ds corrected from impurity losses
- E_{drift} June estimated at ~ 450 V/cm

-> No changes with to November runs

Fig. 10: Stability in the dE/dx response of CRP1 comparing two different cold-box runs CRP1/CRP1b

The noise performance of the readout system is shown in Figure 11. The noise levels were found to be equivalent to the ones of ProtoDUNE Single-Phase.

Fig. 11: Noise levels for all readout channels recorded during the cold-box runs of CRP2 and CRP3

The response uniformity of the channels was checked with an in-situ calibration system capable of performing charge injection from the same signal source individually to each readout channel present in the ASIC amplifiers with 1% accuracy. As shown in Figure 12, without applying any correction, the response uniformity of the channels is at the level of 2.5%, while the average response between different runs for all channels is within 1%.

Fig. 12: Spread of measured calibration constants for all readout channels during the 3 CRP cold-box runs

After the conclusion of the cold-box tests the entire system to read out two Top-Drift CRP was installed in 2023 in NP02 for the Vertical-Drift Module-0 and recommissioned on the NP02 cryostat.

The implementation of the Top-Drift electronics Elements for the readout of the second DUNE Far detector module FD2 is summarized in Figure 13. In FD2 the chimneys are larger and can contain up to 48 front-end cards being connected to four microTCA crates. The readout electronics elements represented in the sketch are the same as the ones validated during the CRP cold-box tests performed at CERN in 2022.

Fig. 13: Summary sketch of the implementation of the Top-Drift Electronics elements for the readout of a large chimney of the DUNE second Far Detector module

3. REFERENCES

[1] NP02 Collaboration (2022) *Yearly progress report on NP02* CERN-SPSC-2022-014; SPSC-SR-308 (2022) <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2805710>

ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
CB	Cold-Box cryostat/Time Projection Chamber
CRP	Charge Readout Plane (3x3.3m ² readout unit of Vertical Drift)
DUNE	Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment
FD-2	Second DUNE Far Detector module (15 kton active LAr mass)
FE	Front-End
FR4	Flame Retardant 4 (PCB material)
LAr	Liquid Argon
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
TDE	Top Drift Electronics
TPC	Time Projection Chamber
VD	Vertical Drift